

University of Helsinki Data Management Plan guidance 2020

This is an updated version of the guidance for writing data management plans at the University of Helsinki. The structure and the content follows the [General Finnish DMP recommendations](#). The guidance text has been modified and tailored by the University of Helsinki Data Support.

Please cite as: University of Helsinki Data Support (4.6.2020).
UH DMP Guidance 2020. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5226844>

Introduction	University of Helsinki DMP guidance
<p>Motivation</p>	<p>Why should you manage your research data?</p> <p>Research data management and its planning are integral parts of good research practices. Data management aims to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • recognize and control the risks involved, • pay attention to data protection and information security, • agree about data ownership, sharing, and preservation, as well as • ensure that the necessary resources and equipment are available. <p>Your Data Management Plan (DMP) should describe how you manage data during as well as after the active phase of the research project. The plan should be updated as the research project evolves. Your research data management practices should aim to produce reusable data, which follows FAIR principles, that is, your data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable.</p> <p>In the DMP data is understood as a broad term including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data collected by various methods (such as surveys, interviews, measurements, imaging techniques etc.), • data produced during the research (such as analysis results), • research sources (such as archive material), • notes and field notes, and • source code and software. <p>How do I write a DMP?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read all of the questions first! • Use the DMP to complement your research plan – avoid overlaps and refer between plans when needed. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The research plan describes the scientific, analytical and methodological processing of data. ○ The data management plan describes the technical and administrative management of data.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the DMP as a risk evaluation document – it shows that you can recognize, anticipate and handle the risks related to your data management workflow. • Follow the organisation’s or funder’s requirements. • Do not copy/paste examples from somewhere else and write only sentences you yourself understand. • Answer at least the main categories – each sub-question does not need to be answered separately. If a certain question is not applicable in your case, justify why not. • Include background information such as the name of the applicant and the project, the project number, the funding programme and the version of the DMP. <p>Good luck with your DMP!</p>
<p align="center">1. General description of the data</p>	
<p>1.1 What kinds of data is your research based on? What data will be collected, produced or reused? What file formats will the data be in? Additionally, give a rough estimate of the size of the data produced/collected.</p>	<p>Discuss the following in your answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What data will be used and produced in the project? If you use sensitive data, see the recommendations below the examples. • In which file formats will the data be in? • Approximately how much data will the project have? • Will you use or develop special software? <p>Tips for best practices</p> <p>Categorize your data in the following way using bullet points or a table, and use the same categorization in all phases of your plan. Your answer to this question forms a general structure for the rest of the plan.</p> <p><i>Example 1:</i></p> <p>1. Data collected for this project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire x, file format .pdf, size 5Gb • DNA samples (n=500) • Pictures/videos about x, file format .jpg, .avi, size 1Tb <p>2. Data produced as an outcome of the process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyses of questionnaire x, .pdf, .xlsx, 1Gb • DNA sequences/analyses, FASTA, .txt, .xlsx, 2Tb • Documentation of the data (readme files, data dictionary, laboratory notebooks) <p>3. Previously collected existing data reused in this project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Samples from the Biobank

- Data from Statistics Finland, database, 10 Gb
- Survey data from Finnish Social Science database Aila
- Interviews or language corpus from the Language Bank of Finland

Example 2:

Data type	Source	File format	Sensitivity	Size
Questionnaire x	data collected	.csv, .txt, .docx	no/yes	1 Gb
Analysis of questionnaire x	data produced	.xlsx, .tif		100 Mb
DNA samples	data reused from Biobank			

Guidance for sensitive data

It is important to identify sensitive data types, as data management planning includes recognizing and managing the risks involved with such data. If your data contains personal data, you need to identify the controller. More information can be found in the Data protection guide for researchers (Flamma).

Sensitive data is information that could cause damage if revealed.

- Personal data:
 - Personal information includes all identifiers from which a person is identifiable *directly* or *indirectly*.
 - *Direct identifiers*: name, phone number, social security number, picture, voice, fingerprint, dental chart, etc
 - *Indirect identifiers*: gender, age, education, profession, nationality, work history, system log history, marital status, residence information, car license number, etc.
- Sensitive personal information:
 - Special categories of personal data:
 - Data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs or trade union membership
 - Genetic data
 - Biometric data processed for the purpose of uniquely identifying a person
 - Data concerning health
 - Data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation
 - Other sensitive personal data:
 - Data describing economic or social status

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Location data ▪ Communication data ▪ Behaviour ▪ Other data that is particularly personal e.g, notes and diaries <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive information about species, such as <u>endangered animals, plants, nature conservation areas, or biosafety (FIN)</u>. • Other confidential information, such as patents, military information, organizational information, or trade secrets.
<p>1.2 How will the consistency and quality of data be controlled?</p>	<p>Discuss the <i>risks</i> involved in controlling <i>data integrity</i> and <i>quality</i>, as well as how they are managed. Notice that data quality and the quality of research methods are two distinct things.</p> <p>Tips for best practices</p> <p>Describe the following practices, if they are/will be in use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you use data management tools, such as a database for data collection? • Has everyone handling the data been introduced to the best practices? • Are the methods validated, or are quality control pipelines in use? • Are transcriptions of audio or video interviews checked by someone other than the transcriber? • Are checksums used (software)? • Digitizing of analog or physical material should be done with sufficient accuracy. • In all conversions, maintaining the original information content should be ensured. • Discuss how <u>minimisation, pseudonymisation, and anonymisation</u> affect data quality.
<p style="text-align: center;">2. Ethical and legal compliance</p>	
<p>2.1 What legal issues are related to your data management? (For example, GDPR and other legislation affecting data processing.)</p>	<p>Discuss the following in your answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does your data include personal information? • Does your work with animals require an ethical permit? • Do you work with other confidential or sensitive data than described above (e.g., <u>endangered species (FIN)</u>, conservation areas, military information)? • Are there Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) such as copyrights involved with the data? <p>Describe how you will maintain high ethical standards and comply with relevant legislation when managing your research data. Describe what are the risks involved, and how are they managed.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Justify why you have the right to collect, handle, and preserve data that involves ethical issues, for example, that you have passed an ethical review. • If you handle <u>personal information</u> (more tips behind the link): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mention, who are the parties processing data and who or which organisation is the controller (or is there a joint controllership between the parties) ○ Describe, what kind of personal data you need and why ○ Specify the legal basis for processing of personal data (research carried out in the public interest, consent?) ○ Assess the risk to data subjects that the processing of their data may cause ○ Assess the need for data protection impact assessment (with the help of <u>Preliminary assessment for data protection - form</u>) ○ Perform the <u>data protection impact assessment</u> if needed ○ Describe, how you will secure the processed data and the privacy of the data subjects (examinees) and if needed, how you perform data <u>anonymisation or pseudonymisation</u>. ○ Assess how you will fulfill <u>the data subject rights</u> (including informing) ○ Describe, how you will take care of the erasure of unnecessary data and <u>what happens after your research</u> <p>Additional information</p> <p>For example, other requirements apply to informing participants and documenting the processing of personal data. You can find more information about them in the links below.</p> <p><u>Data protection guide for researchers</u> (Flamma) <u>General information about data protection</u> (Flamma) <u>Informing research participants</u> (Data management guidelines, FSD) <u>Data protection recommendation for GLAM sector</u> (FIN, Finnish GLAM jurisprudence group) <u>Research ethics</u> (Flamma)</p>
<p>2.2 How will you manage the rights of the data you use, produce and share?</p>	<p>Describe what has been agreed about data usage rights. Consider if there are rights belonging to a third party. Anticipate what licenses will be used when data is opened.</p> <p>Guidance about data ownership and licenses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data ownership rights depend on research funding. Ensure that the necessary agreements have been made in the beginning of the project (data ownership & authorship). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Many funding agencies (Academy of Finland, EU) require data ownership to be transferred to the university. ○ <u>Instructions on concluding an agreement</u> (Flamma)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use a license when opening your data for reuse (e.g. research data, code, software). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The UH recommends the CC0 license for research data, with which you waive your rights to the work. You retain your moral rights, and good scientific practice still stipulates that the author be mentioned. Alternative licenses: ○ UH Library Open Access Creative Commons license guide ○ GNU or MIT licenses <p>Additional information Research ethics (Flamma) Legal aspects & research integrity UH</p> <p>University of Helsinki research data policy</p>
3. Documentation and metadata	
<p>3.1 How will you document your data in order to make the data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable for you and others? What kind of metadata standards, README files or other documentation will you use to help others to understand and use your data?</p>	<p>Explain how you will document your data during the project. Documentation means describing the data, i.e., these documents explain what data the project has and where the data originates from.</p> <p>Documentation includes data dictionaries (explaining variables and codes) and readme files. Other important issues include file naming conventions, version control, and directory structure. There are standard methods available for documentation called metadata standards, which should be used if suitable for the data. These will increase the value of the data by making it easier to reuse. The documentation guide for UH researchers is available in HULib's Zenodo collection.</p> <p>Tips for best practices</p> <p>Discuss the following practices, if they are/will be in use. Further explanations and examples can be found in the documentation guide.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata standards: Many storage services require data to be saved using a standard. Hence, if you know where you will open data, check their standard requirements. • Data management software, i.e., databases and an electronic laboratory notebook • Data dictionaries, which explain variables, or code books, which gather all of the codes and calculations used. • File naming conventions • Directory structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Remember, if metadata, i.e., file, directory, or variable names, include sensitive data or personal information, they need to be handled accordingly. • Readme file(s) provide information about data files to ensure they are interpreted correctly.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version control
4. Storage and backup during the research project	
4.1 Where will your data be stored, and how will the data be backed up?	<p>Consider the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where will your data be stored and <u>backed up</u> during the project? • Who is responsible for backups? • Make a plan with your partners and ensure secure data transfer. <p>Opening, publishing, and archiving data after the project will be described in section five.</p> <p>Tips for best practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the IT Services provided and maintained by the University of Helsinki: <u>storing solution-excel</u>. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ More information: <u>Helpdesk & CSC services</u> for data storage ○ For example use personal / <u>group storage spaces</u>, which are maintained and backed up (every hour) by the UH Centre for Information Technology ○ Cloud storage options: Use the <u>UH OneDrive for business</u> or the Teams cloud instead of commercial services (e.g., Google drive/Dropbox). ○ Do NOT USE external hard drives as the main storing option. <p>Does your project have sufficient storage space? If not, please contact <u>Helpdesk</u> at tel. +358 (0)2 941 55555 or <u>helpdesk@helsinki.fi</u>.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you work with sensitive data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Be sure that your storage is safe enough for the data, e.g. a dedicated UH or CSC secure storage space (Umpio, storage server, ePouta...). ○ Do not use a cloud storage due to its insufficient data protection! ○ Encryption: If needed, particularly mobile devices, portable and external storage devices should be encrypted for use, e.g., <u>Cryptomator</u>. ○ Please, be in contact with <u>datasupport@helsinki.fi</u> if you are unsure about data protection. <p>Additional information <u>Using & storing</u> (UH Research data management) <u>UH Research data management services</u></p>
4.2 Who will be responsible for controlling access to	<p>Answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Who</i> is responsible for controlling access to the data?

<p>your data, and how will secured access be controlled?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>How</i> will the access control be carried out? Is there an IT solution (e.g., password protection, usage logs, or some physical solution (file cabinet) in use? • <i>Who</i> in the research group has access to which data? • <i>Why</i> has each access right (editing, watching, deleting) been awarded? • Tell how information security and the risks from sensitive data have been taken into account. Will sensitive data be stored in an encrypted form? More tips are below. <p>Tips for best practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you use a personal or shared <u>network</u> drive, you can easily control access rights. • <u>Access control</u> of sensitive data should be well considered. Data handling and transferring needs to be in line with permissions. • Access control: There must be a list of users and all rights granted, and a procedure for withdrawing rights. • Monitoring: How will data usage be monitored during the study: can the technical equipment log who used, when, and what data? Ask IT services what kind of automatic usage and change log is provided. • Security of the premises: Check the locking options of workspaces, safe lockers and cabinets, and camera and access surveillance. <p>Additional information</p> <p>National Cyber Security Centre: Ohje lokitietojen tallentamiseen ja hyödyntämiseen (FIN)</p> <p>UH Helpdesk at tel. +358 (0)2 941 55555 or helpdesk@helsinki.fi</p>
<p>5. Opening, publishing and archiving the data after the research project</p>	
<p>5.1 What part of the data can be made openly available or published? Where and when will the data, or its metadata, be made available?</p>	<p>Review all your data types, and answer the following questions (you can refer to the table in Section 1, if you used one):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What part of the <i>data</i> will be opened/published? • Where will the data be opened? Name the repositories. • When will the data be available? • Will some part of the data be destroyed? <p>If your data cannot be opened, explain why, and tell where the project metadata will be opened.</p> <p>Tips for opening data containing personal information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening and sharing personal data are dictated for example by: what the research participants are informed about when the data are collected, whether the research participant has given their explicit consent, or in what form and for what purposes the information is to be opened or shared.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ When opening, you must ensure that the information is properly protected and, where possible, pseudonymize or anonymize the information. ○ The consent of the subject is required for the opening of the material, from which the research participants are directly identifiable. ○ In some cases, the material may be shared for the originally intended purpose. If you are planning on sharing personal data, please contact the University research lawyers (researchlawyers@helsinki.fi). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Even though data including personal information cannot be opened, its <u>metadata</u>, which do not contain sensitive information, should be opened. <p>Tips for best practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Choose suitable repositories for sharing and opening your data already at the beginning of the project. Check that your data fulfills the repository requirements. ● “As a rule, research data produced under the auspices of the University of Helsinki and related to published research results are open and available for shared use. The discoverability and citability of research data must be ensured.” (<u>University of Helsinki research data policy</u>) ● Where to open data? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Check the recommendations of the publishers, learned societies, and funders of your own field. ○ Where have you or your colleagues in the same field published data? ○ Look for repositories: <u>re3data.org</u>. ○ General repositories: <u>IDA</u>, <u>Zenodo</u>, <u>Dryad</u>, <u>Figshare</u>. ● If you cannot open the data, open your metadata about your project data, e.g., in <u>Zenodo</u> or in national <u>Etsin</u>. ● Choose repositories using <u>persistent identifiers</u> (DOI, URN). ● Remember to give your data a license (see 2.2) <p>Additional information <u>UH principles of open publishing</u> <u>Tutkijan muistilista tutkimusdatan julkaisemiseen</u> (Responsible Research)</p>
<p>5.2 Where will data with long-term value be archived, and for how long?</p>	<p>Discuss where data with long-term value is archived and for how long.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What part of the data is archived? ● Where will it be archived? ● For how long will the data be preserved? ● Are there some costs related to archiving? Who takes care of them? ● Will some part of the data be destroyed?

	<p>An archiving plan is part of research quality and transparency.</p> <p>Tips for best practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When data is created, it is important to consider how long it will be preserved. • Check publisher-related preservation time requirements, if you plan to publish in a journal that demands opening your data. • Check discipline-specific and funder-related preservation time requirements. • Personal data may also be archived. When transferring research material containing personal data to the archive, the identification of individuals should, as far as possible, be removed unless there are proper grounds for archiving them, due to the nature of the data. The subjects must also be informed of the archiving and the basis on which the archiving is based. The appropriate protection of personal data, ie who has access to the data and why, must continue to be taken into account when archiving the material. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The UH offers guidance on safe preservation methods. If you are preserving sensitive personal information, contact datasupport@helsinki.fi. • Biological samples can be stored in biobanks. • Fairdata-PAS is a preservation place for nationally valuable data for dozens or hundreds of years. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ More information about UH service queue for Fairdata-PAS here. <p>Links to general guides and additional information</p> <p>Five steps in deciding what data to keep (DCC, UK) UH Archiving plan (Flamma) UH Research data services Data disposal (Data management guidelines, FSD)</p>
6. Data management responsibilities and resources	
<p>6.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e., the data steward)?</p>	<p>Summarise and describe the roles and responsibilities here. Answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Who</i> is responsible for data management tasks? • <i>Who</i> is monitoring data protection and information security? <p>Tips for best practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are data management responsibilities allocated to one person, or is the whole research group involved? • Who is responsible for ensuring that everyone has received the necessary training and everyone follows same practices.

<p>6.2 What resources will be required for your data management procedures to ensure that the data can be opened and preserved according to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?</p>	<p>Describe <i>what resources</i> (time and workload) are needed for data management? The better the planning for data management in the beginning of the project, the less work is needed when data is opened and preserved.</p> <p>Tips for best practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate whether expert help/an assistant is needed for data management, data preservation, and data sharing tasks. • Give an estimate of how much time is needed for data documentation and cleaning to prepare the data (not results) to be opened: 1–2 h weekly, one day per month, 1–2 weeks before publishing, or some other time estimate. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data documentation and cleaning means, for example, producing metadata (section 3.1), anonymising sensitive data, arranging data, transferring data etc. ○ It is recommended to keep documentation up to date throughout the project life cycle. • Specify your data archiving, opening, and publishing costs in the budget according to funder requirements.
--	--